

THE BRITISH COUNCIL

REGIONAL DIRECTORATE DUBAI

TELEPHONE: 22619 CABLES: BRITCOUN P. O. BOX 1636

DUB/0520/2

20 September 1971

Miss Beatrice de Cardi
Council for British Archaeology
8 St Andrew's Place
London
NW1

Dear Miss de Cardi,

I telephoned you when I was home on leave this summer, but unfortunately left it just a few days too late, as you had just gone away on holiday. A pity as I had been looking forward to seeing you again.

There was also yet another Dubai project I was trying to enlist your help for. I told you that they have started a museum here and volunteered me as custodian. What has happened now is that everyone connected with the museum (and especially myself) has realised that nothing very constructive can be done by part-time workers: after four months or so even the preliminary inventory is not finished. So the Dubai Municipality has agreed that we should try and find someone with relevant interests or qualifications to come and work on it full-time for a year, re-arrange the existing exhibits properly classified and labelled and also travelling round collecting more. The Municipality has agreed to provide a furnished flat, transport and all supporting services (like secretarial help and skilled and unskilled labour) and would also pay a living wage.

Obviously we shan't get a professional museum worker on these terms. What we were thinking of was the possibility of finding someone who had just finished a degree or research in, say, Arabic, archaeology, Islamic history or some similar field, who would enjoy doing a job like this for a short time for the sake of the experience and of pursuing his (or her) own interests. The money will be enough to live comfortably on, but not to save on.

The Museum is very unsophisticated. It is really a kind of folk museum at present, containing household stuff, weaponry, camelry and saddlery - the kind of things you would have found in every house

/s...

twenty years ago, but which are now fast disappearing from the scene. There are huge gaps even here; and as for expansion, it could take any direction the new curator wanted. It is in fact at the level where a bit of drive and organisation and common sense may be more important than detailed specialist knowledge.

This idea was really mine. I knew the Municipality couldn't afford to pay a full ~~time~~ professional salary and all that goes with it, and I thought an enthusiastic ex-student would at least keep the project from languishing. I remembered that when I left Oxford there were four or five people I knew who would have jumped at a year off like this. What I hadn't remembered was that when I went home everyone would be on vacation: consequently most of the people I had intended to talk to about it (including you) were away.

Can you help at all on this? Or if not directly, can you approach people in universities who might have some candidates? It could be either a man or a woman - in fact a woman would have more scope in some ways than a man. We really need someone as soon as possible. As I say, I was hoping to recruit someone this summer to start about now. It's getting a bit late, but I'm hoping there may still be someone suitable who hasn't got fixed up for the coming academic year. It's a lovely job for someone who likes bumping around the wadis in a Land Rover and who would like to run an interesting project on his own.

I enclose a copy of Kamal Hanza's letter authorising recruitment. You will see that terms are very vague, but we can get the details arranged very fast if we get a likely candidate.

With best wishes from me and Kate

Yours ever

David

David Phillips
Regional Director

Are you coming out this year?